

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF THICK COMPOSITE PIPES REINFORCED WITH MULTILAYER BRAID

Y. Shimizu^{1*}, K. Hashimoto¹, T. Uozumi², A. Ohtani², A. Nakai²

¹ Research & Development Dept, TMT Machinery, Inc., Kyoto, Japan,

² Gifu University, Gifu, Japan

* Corresponding author (shimizu-y@tmt-mc.jp)

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1 Introduction

Composite materials have been used mainly in the aerospace and aircraft industries for over 30 years. In recent years housing, automotive, civil engineering, and sporting goods have become important application fields. However, for continued expansion of the application of composite materials they must offer not only light weight and high strength, but also functional properties and reduced costs. Researchers in applied mechanics have made progress in developing the anisotropic theory, the lamination theory, and the newer failure criterion, so that a design method has been established for large-scale panels made from unidirectional composites. When we consider the cost of composite materials, fabrication or manufacturing cost cannot be ignored. The selection of an appropriate manufacturing system is important, and research related to manufacturing will be needed.

Textiles such as woven, knitted, and braided fabrics possess high potential for the fabrication of near-net-shape composites. This means that textile composites can reduce manufacturing costs greatly compared to unidirectional prepreg composites. However, the low mechanical properties of textile composites are caused by undulation of the fiber bundle and low fiber volume fractions. These characteristics currently limit the use of textile composites in many structurally critical applications. Accordingly, textile composites with high mechanical properties will be an important goal.

Tubular elements have been widely used in structural application. Generally the reinforcements are laminated in thick tube members by using filament winding method and conventional tubular braiding technique. However, due to an occurrence of the interlamina delamination and difficulty to fabricate complex shaped components with these techniques, these materials are limited in their

application for structural parts. Also, the superior mechanical properties can't be obtained in the laminated composite tubes.

In order to prohibit the occurrence of the interlamina delamination, the reinforced fibers in the thickness direction of the composite are necessary. There are some textile techniques such as stitching and 3-D weaving in which the concept of the through-the-thickness reinforcement can be utilized [1,2]. These techniques need additional process during fabricating process. It is difficult to form cylindrical shape by using these techniques. Recently, we have proposed that the lamina can be connected by using binding fibers in the braiding techniques [3].

The braiding promises improvements in properties of the composite material and to meet the requirements of automated fabrication. Using the braiding three dimensional fiber preforms of near-net shape of the component can be easily made [4,5].

In this paper, two different braiding systems were proposed in order to enhance the strength of thick composite tubes. In particular, the objective was to achieve high strength by controlling the occurrence and propagation of delaminations. A conventional laminated tube under lateral compressive loading will fail as a result of delamination, an inherent failure mode in this type of material. In the proposed tubes, braiding fibers were oriented through the laminae, so it was expected that delamination growth would be impeded. There are two braiding systems: the multi-reciprocal braiding process and the multi-layered braiding process. In order to explain these systems the concept of the dimension of braiding mechanisms was introduced. The braiding mechanism consists of the spindle movement and the take-up movement. According to the concept of the dimension of each movement, the sum of these

Figure 1. Tubular braiding machine and illustration of conventional tubular braiding system

dimensions expresses the degree of the braided fabric. Further, compressive tests for the multi-reciprocal braid pipes were carried out, and bending tests for the multi-layered braid were also carried out. These test results indicated that the proposed system could be for high-strength thick composite tubes.

2 Braiding System

2-1 Conventional Braiding process and Dimension of Braiding Mechanism

Figure 1 shows a photograph of a tubular braiding machine and an illustration of the conventional tubular braiding system. Spindles move along a circular track and the mandrel moves axially. One group of spindles moves on the track in clockwise, and the other group of spindles moves in counterclockwise. When the tubular braid is fabricated, a mandrel is set up at the center of the braiding machine. All fiber bundles supplied from their spindles wrap around the surface of the mandrel. They were intertwined to form braided fabric on the mandrel. Generally, several layers or plies of fabric are braided over each other over and

over again to produce the required thickness (over braiding).

The braiding angle, the angle between the direction of the fiber bundle and the longitudinal direction, is determined by the relative speed between the spindle movement and the take-up movement.

The braiding mechanism consists of the take-up

Figure 2. 1D+1D Braiding mechanism.

mechanism and the spindle movement. Figure 2 illustrates the two movements. The spindle movement along the circle can be regarded as one-dimensional movement. The formed fabric is taken up in the vertical direction which is also a one-dimensional movement. Simple shapes such as tubular braids and flat braids can be fabricated by a combination of these two one-dimensional movements. This conventional braiding mechanism is indicated as 1D+1D (spindle movement + take-up movement). Conceptually, any class of dimension can be combined, for example, 2D + 1D, 2D + 2D, 3D + 1D, 3D + 2D, etc. As the total dimension or the sum of each movement is increased, more complex shapes of braided preforms can be fabricated.

Next, as an example of 2D + 1D, Figure 3 shows a schematic diagram of braiding mechanism for an I-shaped braid. The spindles move two-dimensionally according to the shape of the cross section. Here, the take-up movement is still one-dimensional. However, the sum of the two movements becomes three-dimensional, so that complex-shaped braids have been realized. Occasionally, these preforms are called integrated preforms.

2-2 Multi-Reciprocal Braiding Process and Fabrication of Self-reinforced Multilayer Braid

2.2.1 Multi-Reciprocal Braiding Process

The multi-reciprocal braiding process is a 1D + 1DR mechanism. The spindle movement is the same as in the conventional braiding mechanism as described in the previous section. On the other hand,

Figure 3. 2D+1D Braiding mechanism.

an additional take-up mechanism was used, that is, a reversible motion, and 1DR means one-dimensional with reversible movement. When the reversible movements are added to the mandrel as shown in Figure 4, a multi-reciprocal tube can be fabricated. At the reverse point, braiding fibers orient to the thickness direction. Actually, the reversible movement was repeated at periodic intervals.

2.2.2 Fabrication of Self-reinforced Multilayer Braid

The Self-reinforced Multilayer braided composite tube fabricated by the multi-reciprocal braiding process is termed a multi-reciprocal tube. The braided composite tube with interlaminar reinforcement can be fabricated by the technique shown in Figure 5. During the braiding process, the reversible points change. First, three layers are fabricated by the normal reciprocal process at part A and then the third layer comes on top the first layer at part B. Therefore, braiding fibers oriented in the thickness direction at the interlaminar region between parts A and B. It is expected that through-the-thickness fabric of the braided composite tube would suppress the growth of delamination in a thick composite.

Figure 4. Reversible mandrel movement.

Braided fabric is oriented into the thickness direction at reversible points

Figure 5. Fabrication process of Self-reinforced multilayer braid.

2-3 Multi-Layered Braiding Process and Fabrication of Multilayer Braid with through-the-thickness fibers

2.3.1 Multi-Layered Braiding Process

Figure 6 shows a photograph of a Multi-layered braiding machine. And, Figure 7 illustrates the track configuration for fabricating a multi-layered braided fabric. Spindles move on all circular tracks through the connecting parts indicated with the hatch in the figure. Therefore, this mechanism was called the 1DM + 1D mechanism, where M stands for multi-layer. The take-up movement was one-dimensional, whereas the spindle movement is basically restricted to a circular movement. However, some braiding fibers go through the outer, middle, and inner tracks, and these fibers can prevent interlaminar fracture, resulting in high strength. The reinforcing fibers orient continuously to adjacent layers.

2.3.2 Fabrication of Multi-Layered Braid with through-the-thickness fibers

Braided composite tubes fabricated by

Figure 6. Multi-layered braiding machine.

Figure 7. Track configuration of multi-layered braiding machine.

Figure 8. Multi-layered braid with through-the-thickness.

layered tubes. The machine bed for this process consists of three tracks linked together at the connecting parts as shown in Figure 5(a). Three groups of spindles move on the track of each layer in the clockwise direction as shown in Figure 5(b). The spindles of another group move through the connecting parts in the counter-clockwise direction. Therefore, the fibers supplied from these spindle groups form not only the tubular braided fabrics in each layer but also the through-the-thickness fibers. The fabricated braid is illustrated in Figure 8. The notable feature of this braided fabric is a thick tubular braided fabric without distinct non-interlacing lamina, since one group of braiding fiber bundles provides interlaminar reinforcement and forms the braided fabric. The number of layers can be extended beyond three by modifying the machine bed.

3 Mechanical Properties

3-1 Lateral Compressive Test for Self-reinforced Multilayer Braid

multi-layered braiding process are called multi-

The lateral compressive behaviors of the multi-reciprocal tube and the multi-layered tube were examined. A laminated three-layer tube made by conventional braiding was also prepared for comparison. The reinforcement for the self-reinforced multilayer braid made by multi-reciprocal braiding was E-glass fibers of 1100tex (Nitto Boseki Co. Ltd.). For the matrix, epoxy resin (EPICLON830: Dainippon Ink and Chemical, Inc.) was used. In the case of the multi-layered braid pipe, glass fiber (ER2310F-165, Nippon Electric Glass Co, Ltd.) and epoxy resin (EPOMIK R-140, Mitsui Petro-Chemical Industry Co.) were also used. As the reinforcement fiber and matrix for laminated braid pipes, the above two types of glass fiber and epoxy resin were prepared. RTM was used to fabricate the composite specimens.

Figure 9 shows the shape of the specimen. The specimen lengths of the multi-reciprocal tube and the multi-layered tube were 25 mm and 45 mm, respectively. The inside diameter of both specimens was 17.5 mm, and the outside diameters of the multi-reciprocal tube and the multi-layered tube were 21.5 mm and 19.0 mm, respectively. The outside diameter of the laminated tube is the same as that of the respective self-reinforced tube. The braiding angle of both tubes was 60 degrees, and the fiber volume fraction was about 60%.

The specimen is placed between the upper and lower plates and is deformed by pushing down the upper plate, as shown in Figure 10. Lateral compressive tests were carried out using an Instron Universal Testing Machine (Type 4206) at a testing speed of mm/min.

Figure 11 shows the relation between lateral compressive and displacement for the multi-reciprocal tube and the laminated tube. Figure 11 does not exhibit curves by the final fracture. Both specimens exhibited a linear increase of load at small displacement. After the load reached the maximum value, sudden reductions of load were observed in the case of laminated tubes. On the other hand, the load reached the maximum value of almost the same value in the case of the multi-reciprocal tube. This is due to the difference in the fracture propagation. From the visual observation during testing, the delamination occurred at one of the edges of the laminated tubes and propagated

Figure 9. Lateral compressive test specimen.

Figure 10. Lateral compressive test method.

Figure 11. Load-displacement curves of multi-reciprocal tube.

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Table 1 Lateral compressive properties of Multi-Reciprocal braid pipe and laminated braid pipe.

	Lateral Compressive Modulus (GPa)	Lateral Compressive Strength (MPa)	Energy Absorption (J)
Multi-Reciprocal Braid	5.00	410	5.61
Laminated Braid	5.19	374	4.96

rapidly along the axial direction from one edge to the other. In contrast, in the case of the multi-reciprocal tube, the propagation of delamination along the axial direction which occurred at one of the edges was impeded at the reversible points. Therefore, a sudden reduction in load was not observed in multi-reciprocal tubes.

Table 1 lists the lateral compressive modulus and strength of the multi-reciprocal tube and the laminated tube. The lateral compressive modulus of the multi-reciprocal tube is nearly equal to that of the laminated tube, whereas the lateral compressive strength of multi-reciprocal tubes is higher than that of laminated tubes, so it is concluded that the interlaminar strength was enhanced by the through-the thickness fabric. Moreover, the energy absorption to a displacement of 3.5mm was 5.61 J in the case of the multi-reciprocal tube, whereas the energy absorption of the laminated tube was 4.96 J.

These results indicate the value of fiber bundles that are oriented through the thickness.

3-2 Binding Test for Multilayer Braid with through-the-thickness fibers

The reinforcement and matrix used were glass fiber (diameter of 17 μ m, 2000 filaments, ER1155 F-165, Nippon Electric Glass Co., Ltd.) and epoxy resin (EPOMIK R-140, Mitsui Petro Chemical Industry Co.), respectively. Three kinds of fiber orientation angles (braiding angle) with reference to the longitudinal direction of the specimen, 20, 30 and 40 degrees were chosen. For comparison, laminated braid pipes with same braiding angles were fabricated by using the same braiding machine. Three tracks are independent to each other in this case. The multiple layer braided tube consists of three layers of tubular braids, and the number of

Table 2 Bending properties of thick braided tubes and multiple layer braided tube.

	Through-the-thickness Braid			Laminated Braid		
	20	30	40	20	30	40
Braiding Angle (deg.)	20	30	40	20	30	40
Bending Modulus (GPa)	22.3	12.8	14.5	22.7	10.9	9.75
(Ratio *)	(0.98)	(1.17)	(1.49)			
Bending Strength (MPa)	407	280	293	413	237	205
(Ratio *)	(0.99)	(1.18)	(1.43)			

spindles of laminated braid pipe in each layer was equal to that of thick braided tube. PTM was used to fabricate the composite specimen.

Four point bending tests were carried out. The support and loading spans were 240mm and 80mm, respectively. Dimensions of the specimen were 17.5mm inner diameter and length 160mm for bending test. The bending tests were performed at testing speed 1mm/min. and room temperature.

Table 2 shows the bending properties of the thick braided tubes compared with the data of multiple layer braided tubes. Ratios of modulus and strength mean the values which divide those of the thick braided tube by those of the multiple layer braided tube, respectively. For braiding angle 20 the bending modulus and strength of the thick braided tube was equal to those of the multiple layer braided tube. However, they were higher than those of the multiple layer braided tubes for the braiding angles 30 and 40. The ratios of the modulus and strength increased with increase of the braiding angle. The thick braided tubes possessed superior bending properties compared to the multiple layer braided tubes for the braiding angle 30 or more.

In all types of specimens the ultimate failure occurs at compression side. From the cross section observation of a fracture area, the interlamina delamination could be observed in the case of the multiple layer braided tube, however such fracture was never observed in the case of the thick braided tube. It is considered that the through-the thickness fibers have prohibited the interlamina delamination.

4 Conclusion

Two different braiding systems were proposed to enhance the strength of thick composite tubes. Two types of self-reinforced tubes, multi-reciprocal tubes and multi-layered tubes, were fabricated and their lateral compressive properties were examined. In the case of the multi-reciprocal tube, the propagation of delamination at the edge was impeded by fiber bundles oriented through the thickness, whereas in the case of the multi-layered tube, delamination was restrained by the fiber bundles oriented in the thickness direction. It is considered that the proposed braiding systems can

be used for enhancing the strength of thick composite tubes.

References

- [1] A.Nisimura, N.Ueda and H.Matsuda: "New Fabric Structures of Carbon Fiber", 28th National SAMPE Symposium,(1983),71-88.
- [2] P.S.Bruno, D.O.Keith and A.A.Vicari, Jr.: "Automatically Woven Three-Directional Composite structures", 31th International SAMPE Symposium,(1986), 7-10.
- [3] A.Yokoyama, A.Fujita, H.Kobayashi, H.Hamada and Z.Maekawa:"Failure Process of Composite Tubes with Braided Structure", The 1989 ASME Pressure Vessels and Piping Conference – JSME Co-sponsorship, Vol.167, (1989), 147-152.
- [4] A.Yokoyama, A.Fujita, H.Kobayashi, H.Hamada and Z.Maekawa: "A New Braiding Process – Robotised Braiding Mechanism", Materials and Processing - Move into the 90's, (1989),87-99.
- [5] H.Kobayashi, N.Nakama, Z.Maekawa, H.Hamada, A.Fujita and T.Uozumi: "Fabrication and Mechanical Properties of Braided Composite Truss Joint", 37th International SAMPE Symposium and Exhibition, (1992), 1089-1103.